

1. Introduction

Thanks for taking the time to meet with me today.

We are doing a study on the security practices for smart contract development. During the interview, I'd like to ask you a few questions about your background, then we will discuss your experience.

Do you mind if I record this discussion so that I can review it later? In any data collected, or in reports or papers that are published, you will not be identified by name. Please be careful not to discuss any sensitive information about the company you work for. If you do mention any, we will do our best to remove it from our transcripts, but better if you don't mention such sensitive information at all.

2. Demographics

2.1 Years of Experience

How many years of development experience do you have in total with software development? And how many years with smart contract development?

	With Smart Contract	Total
Experience (in years)		

2.2 Job Responsibility

Could you please briefly describe your job responsibility with respect to development with smart contracts?

2.3 Experience in Job Responsibility

Next, I'm going to name a series of job responsibilities, and I'd like to tell me where you have "none", "some" or "extensive" experience you have for development with ML and traditional software development.

	With Smart Contract	Traditional Software Development
Programming		
Design		
Management		
Testing		

2.4 Current Team and Project

Team Size (number of people): _____

Blockchain platform: _____

	With Smart Contract	Traditional Software Development
Programming Languages		

3. Open-Ended Discussion

Now, let's discuss your experience with respect to security practices of smart contracts. Let us start with an open-ended conversation.

What are your main priorities when doing the development of smart contracts?

Does your priority change when a deadline is approaching?

What about security? Is it something you worry about?

Have you encountered any security issues for the smart contract deployed in your project? How did you deal with it?

4. Specific Topic Discussion

Ok, let's move on to specific security practices in smart contract development.

4.1 Process

What process does your team use for smart contract development?

(Waterfall/Iterative/Agile/Other)

How does security fit in the process?

What specific tasks with respect to security exist for each phase in the process?

Do you use Test-Driven Development?

How does your team maintain smart contracts?

4.2 Resource and Training

Which resources do you use to gain security knowledge?

Do you get training (formal, or self-learning) to gain a better knowledge of software security? How often?

4.3 Security Practices

What **strategies** do you use to try to ensure the security of smart contracts? (code review, testing)

What **tools** do you use to ensure the security for smart contracts?

What **techniques** do you use to ensure the security for smart contracts?